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Not at All New Metaphysics from a Geologist-Geochemist¹

The article deals with the ancient problem of metaphysics (which is considered as a synonym for philosophy): the status and correlation of the material and spiritual. With the help of Wikipedia and Bertrand Russell's book "A History of Western Philosophy", the author undertook a "survey" of 9 real philosophers (adding Nikolai Berdyaev to them!) and he found out that his intuitive thoughts had actually been expressed in one form or another by great philosophers throughout the 2,600 years of philosophy's existence. Such a coincidence allows us to hope that the metaphysics proposed by the author are not erroneous and boils down to the following

1. Man exists in a world in which there are two parts: the material and the non-material, called virtual.

2. Both of these parts are "sovereign", that is, they are completely independent of each other. This correlation of the parts of the world was recognized only by very few dualistic philosophers. ***This is the first thesis of the author's metaphysics – the sovereign reality (being, existence) of objects of both the Material and Virtual world.***

3. Despite the sovereign status of the Material and Virtual worlds, they have different geological ages: the Virtual appeared on our planet by about 4.5 billion years later than the Material one. This is the age of appearance on planet Earth of a biological species – *Homo sapiens*, which, unlike other creatures, possessed consciousness. Thus, the Virtual is not just a product of the brain, but a product of Consciousness.

4. Everything that can be thought of (that is, everything that can be generated by Consciousness) exists, that is, has a Being. Accordingly, the opposite thesis is also true: what you can't think about does not exist in the Virtual World. So, in particular, Socrates also believed. ***This is the second thesis of the author's metaphysics: the reality of any objects in the Virtual World.***

KEYWORDS: philosophy, metaphysics, history of philosophy, material, virtual, Bertrand Russell, Wikipedia.

For approximately 2600 years now (beginning with the very ancient Greeks, such as **Thales**, who lived in the early 6th century BCE), certain people have been engaged in a rather remarkable pursuit – philosophy. That is, they contemplate matters not directly related to the physical existence of humans, which consists of procuring food and continuing the species.

The practice of philosophy distinguishes humans from other animals, including close relatives – primates. Whether primates possess consciousness

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remains unclear to science thus far; but what is absolutely certain – they have no philosophy – neither macaques, nor even the highly intelligent chimpanzees.

Metaphysics, or Philosophy

Metaphysics is commonly understood as a totality of highly general statements about the World, Being, and that which exists. Most often metaphysics is defined as a part of philosophy, but many consider metaphysics simply a synonym of philosophy. ***It is precisely in this sense (metaphysics = philosophy) that I employ this term here.*** This is done because 'philosophical' in our language has many parasitic (everyday, non-scientific) meanings (for example, '*philosophical attitude toward misfortunes*'), whereas 'metaphysical' in this respect is a more definite and precise concept.

Metaphysics and Geology

However, not one of the great philosophers known to me has been interested in geology. Professional philosophers occupied themselves with anything whatsoever – most often with religion, then history, ethics, psychology, quite frequently – even with politics; from the natural sciences – with astronomy and mathematics (especially geometry), less often with physics, and Kant even created a remarkable scheme for the origin of the Solar System (wherein all the planets were inhabited...).

However, geology never occupied philosophers. And this is not difficult to understand, since practically all the great philosophers lived no later than the 20th century, when modern geology (with isotopic geochronology!) did not yet exist. Therefore, philosophers sought answers to questions about Creation and the Structure of the Universe in religion, rather than in geology.

The present notes, compiled by a geologist (more precisely—a geologist-geochemist), are intended, as one writes in dissertations, 'to fill this gap.'

Science demands rigor of language. Therefore, we shall first engage in the search for definitions (also known as determinations). It has long been proven: one need only define something strictly (unambiguously, as comrade Zhirinovskiy, son of a lawyer, liked to say) – and behold, the problem resolves itself...

The Material and the Virtual

For two millennia now, idealist philosophers have been butting heads with materialist philosophers over the question of Being.

Materialists assert that the World consists of matter without any such nonsense in the form of thoughts (ideas), for ideas are already secondary, generated by that same matter.

Idealists, on the contrary, hold that the World consists precisely of ideas, while matter is something deficient, secondary, generated by these ideas. This is exactly what the greatest idealist believed – **Plato**, who, it is said, was actually

named **Aristocles**, meaning 'best glory'. His influence on philosophy is so enormous that his true name (if this is not a fabrication) suits him far better than the absurd nickname meaning 'broad' – for his broad shoulders, which was valued in Greek gymnastics.

Thus, speaking simply, for materialists Essence (Being) is material (that is, it consists of atoms, of which, together with transuranics, there exist approximately one hundred in Nature, to which in the 20th century elementary particles were also added (for example, protons), as well as physical fields); whereas for idealists, Essence (Being) is non-material, that is, it does not consist of any atoms whatsoever. True, what ideas themselves actually consist of the idealists do not specify, in view of the obvious baseness of such a question...

Therefore, materialists assert that the World exists in and of itself—without any thinking subject reflecting upon it. Idealists, however, maintain that without thought about the World—no World exists at all. When you die, that is, when you cease to think—the World will vanish for you.

We put an end to this endless butting of heads by introducing an absolutely necessary definition CONCERNING TWO TYPES OF BEING (Existence, Reality)—the material and the non-material (**Virtual**).

As is well known, the liver secretes bile, and the stomach – gastric juice. In entirely analogous fashion, the brain, a far more complex human organ – in its functioning generates (so to speak, "secretes") – thoughts. The brain – is entirely material; it consists of atoms assembled into large molecules (primarily of carbon, hydrogen, oxygen, nitrogen, and sulfur – with a minor admixture of approximately 95 other chemical elements). But its functional 'output' – thoughts (which are also ideas, concepts, representations) – are non-material (Virtual), and are not composed of any atoms known to us. However, thoughts, just like the brain, really exist, and it is utterly impossible to refute this.

Thus, Reality (Being, the Existent) – has two types, two varieties – Material and Virtual.

Although both idealists and materialists have long agreed with this, we go much further than both and provide a completely new definition of Virtual Being (the Existent, Reality):

REAL (I.E., POSSESSES EXISTENCE!) IS EVERYTHING ABOUT WHICH ONE CAN THINK. THAT ABOUT WHICH ONE CANNOT THINK DOES NOT EXIST.

If we can think about *Pokémon* (and the clever Japanese, as is well known, have already thought about them) – this means that Pokémon exist, although they are virtual. But if a Pokémon is depicted on a smartphone screen – then it becomes quite material.

If we can think about *the Almighty* (and humanity has been occupied with precisely this for some three thousand years!) – then the Almighty, naturally, exists. As long as no one yet possessed the capacity to think about Him – there was no Almighty in the World either (let us say, 5 thousand years before our era).

At first glance, a perplexing question: did the World exist before the emergence of thinking human beings, say – in the Jurassic period? Since there was no one capable of thought at that time, does it follow that there was no World either? But what of the shells of Jurassic ammonites that a geologist holds in his hands: they are quite real, which means that the ammonites existed, even though no one thought anything about them at the time.

But this question is posed incorrectly. It must be clarified: **about which World precisely** is being discussed? If *about the virtual one*, then it's correct – it did not yet exist then, since there were no thinking subjects: after all, ammonites did not possess the capacity for mind; they only swam, fed, and reproduced.

– But if we today think about the Jurassic *material* World, for example, about Jurassic Park (and about dinosaurs, for instance) – this means they are completely real, they unconditionally existed then (only as material) and exist to this day (being now only virtual).

But our contemporary World of the Quaternary period – that one is quite material indeed. It consists of inorganic matter (primarily oxygen, silicon, aluminum with admixtures of another 97–98 elements) and organic matter (mentioned above in the description of the brain – primarily carbon, hydrogen, oxygen, nitrogen, sulfur with admixtures of the same 95 elements).

And it turns out that with our typification of Essence (Being, Reality) – many venerable human occupations become entirely unnecessary...

For example, **Baruch Spinoza**, a person of genius intellect, strained his outstanding mind to prove the theorem of God's Being. But with our definition – it is evident that he was engaged in an unnecessary endeavor (it would have been better had he invented something useful for preventing silicosis during lens grinding, which brought him to the grave at the age of only 45). Unnecessary because the reality of God requires absolutely no proof. **After all, God is a virtual object – and he is real precisely because we invented him.** If it has been conceived – then it is real!

Or take modern cosmology: physicists fiercely debate the magnitude of the average density of the Universe. At one density value, the Universe expands without limit (and galaxies diverge), while at another – the Universe may, after some billions of years, begin to contract and once again transform into a point with infinitely large density. If one model is correct (= real), then the other is automatically considered incorrect, that is, unreal – non-existent. However, under our definition of Virtual Reality, there is no contradiction whatsoever: both virtual models are real – simply because we were able to conceive them!

Another example: the famous assertion of the celebrated German philosopher **Georg Hegel** that the entire history of human society is nothing other than the Self-Development of the World Spirit (and not the evolution of some vulgar 'means of production,' as was later invented by the ardent Hegelian **Karl Marx**). From the standpoint of impoverished materialism, this Hegelian conception is simply utter nonsense, because there exists, you see, no World Spirit in nature. But. But! But if Georg Hegel thought about this World Spirit (and how he thought about it: with astonishing detail!) – then, consequently, the World

Spirit exists – as one of the objects of the Virtual World. And although Georg Hegel was excessively clever for the Germans, since not one of the Hegelians (except, however, Marx and Engels) truly understood him – the Germans treated him with the greatest respect, – and quite justly so.

The well-forgotten old...

Although we arrived at the definitions formulated above, as simple as they are paradoxical, entirely independently, I suspected that they could not be completely original. '*This cannot be,*' I thought to myself, '*– that they (in one form or another?) – have not been expressed by anyone before.*'

To clarify this (and thereby somewhat reduce my philosophical ignorance), I turned to Bertrand Russell's most famous book. His remarkable work 'A History of Western Philosophy' was written based on a course of lectures delivered by Russell in 1940 at Harvard University – following a whole series of humiliations endured by the lecturer (who at times lacked money even for a bus ticket!), which by no means did honor to the 'cultured society' of the USA, replete with manifestations of the most savage religious fanaticism...

This great book allows me (placing full trust in Russell's exposition) to assess the content of philosophers' works – without undertaking the study of primary sources, which lies beyond my capacity. That is, everything further in this text is the most shameless 'quotation-mongering': ***I leafed through Russell's book and extracted from it only what the great philosophers wrote about the subjects that interest me: namely, about objects of the Material and Virtual World (although they called them differently, for example, 'substance,' 'body,' 'spirit,' 'soul,' or 'sensations').***

Although the great philosophers were most typically interested in *the relationship* between the Material and the Ideal—what matters to me is only the smallest part: what they expressed about one and the other *as such* ('*taken in itself,*' as Georg Hegel would say)—leaving aside their interrelationships.

Besides Russell's survey, *Wikipedia* has also been used below, whose articles are compiled, as one may suppose, by very knowledgeable people.

It is quite remarkable that the quotation-gathering I require can begin with Parmenides – 500 years before our era!

1. Parmenides. From *Wikipedia* one can learn that Parmenides –

ancient Greek philosopher, founder and principal representative of the Eleatic school. He expressed his views in the metaphysical poem 'On Nature' <...> a significant portion of whose fragments have come down to us; it contains the fundamental tenets of Eleatic philosophy. His student and follower was Zeno of Elea. To him trace back the beginnings of metaphysics.

Here is what Russell writes about him [Russell, 2001, p. 46]:

Parmenides was a native of Elea in Southern Italy; the flourishing of his activity falls in the first half of the fifth century B.C. According to Plato, Socrates in his youth (reportedly around 450 B.C.) conversed with Parmenides, at that time a very old man, and drew much from this

conversation. Whether this conversation actually took place or not, we do not know, but at the very least we can conclude that Plato himself was quite evidently under the influence of Parmenides' teaching.

<...> When you think, you think about *something*; when you use some name, it must be the name of *something*. Consequently, both thinking and speech require objects outside themselves. And since you can think a thing or speak of it at any time, everything that can be thought or spoken of must exist always.

Thus, that which can be thought about exists. In this way, Parmenides asserted the existence (Being, Reality) of virtual objects.

2. Anaxagoras (ca. 500 BCE – 428 BCE). From *Wikipedia* one can learn that he was an ancient Greek philosopher, mathematician, and astronomer. Founder of the Athenian philosophical school. When the dark unreasoning Athenians wanted to execute him for freethinking, but persuaded by Pericles, replaced execution with exile, Anaxagoras proudly said: '*It is not I who lost Athens, but the Athenians who lost me.*'

Here is what Russell writes about him [Russell, 2001, p. 55]:

Anaxagoras was born in Ionia at Clazomenae around 500 B.C., but lived in Athens for approximately 30 years (from roughly 462 to 432 B.C.). He was probably invited by Pericles, who sought to civilize his fellow citizens <...>. He was the first to introduce the Athenians to philosophy and the first to express the idea that mind is the primary cause of physical changes.²

<...> He differs from his predecessors in that he considers mind ("nous") as a substance that enters into the composition of living beings and distinguishes them from dead matter. In everything, he said, there is a part of everything, except mind, and some things contain mind as well. Mind has power over all things that possess life; it is infinite and governs itself, it is mixed with non-Being.

Thus, in Anaxagoras's treatment, *nous* is inherent in all living beings, whereas inanimate matter *does not possess nous*. Our understanding of thinking is more narrow – the Anaxagorean *nous* is inherent only to humans. And in contrast to Anaxagoras's pure idealism, we believe that *nous* cannot in any way alter matter. Perhaps Russell's rather obscure expression '*it is mixed with non-being*' can be interpreted thus: no nous – no object of it, that is, no thinking – no Virtual Reality? However, I have no confidence in the correctness of such an interpretation.

3. Plato (between 429 or 427 B.C., Athens – 347 B.C., *ibid.*). From *Wikipedia* one can learn about him that he is an ancient Greek philosopher, student of Socrates, teacher of Aristotle. Plato is the first philosopher whose works have been preserved not in brief fragments quoted by others, but in their entirety.

It is generally accepted that Plato is one of the founders of the idealist direction in world philosophy. In many works of the philosopher, the idea is advanced that Being in the true sense of the word can only refer to absolute essences that preserve their Being irrespective of space and time. Such absolute essences are called in the writings, or *eidoi*. In Plato's dialogue 'Timaeus,' the main narrator arrives at the position according to which the solution to the ontological question depends entirely upon how we resolve questions of epistemology. If we agree that true knowledge concerns only eternal and immutable Being, whereas regarding the changing and temporal there can be no true knowledge but only opinion, then we must acknowledge the autonomous existence of ideas.

² Ionia was a Greek-inhabited region on the western coast of Asia Minor by the Aegean Sea; currently territories adjacent to Izmir in Turkey. Includes a narrow coastal strip from Phocaea to Miletus; the islands of Chios and Samos. Borders Aeolia to the north, Lydia to the east, and Caria to the south. The main population consisted of Ionians. ([Wikipedia](#))

<...> Among researchers there exist contradictory judgments concerning the status that Plato ascribes to ideas. It is evident that by ideas Plato understands not merely a concept of a thing, but the cause and purpose of its existence. In the dialogue «Parmenides» Plato criticizes the cardinal opposition between the «World of ideas» and the «World of things». In this dialogue the character intended to represent the historically existing philosopher Parmenides undertakes to prove the absurdity of the assertion that ideas exist separately from things. In many respects, Plato's critique of the dualism of things and ideas is repeated in the later works of Aristotle. The conclusion of the 'Parmenides' testifies to the fact that the question of the existence of the idea is a question of the existence of the One in general. If the One exists, it cannot remain the One in the strict sense of the word. The Plato scholar Tatiana Vadimovna Vasilyeva states the following regarding this problem: *'the One can remain the One, and only the One, the one and only One, only as long as it does not exist. As soon as the one becomes an existing one, it ceases to be merely one and becomes many. There is a contradiction here, but this is a contradiction of Being itself. Does this conclusion reject the separate existence of ideas? In a monistic system it does reject it, in a dualistic one it does not.*

Here is what Russell writes about Plato's dialogue 'Theaetetus' concerning Virtual Reality [Russell, 2001, p. 114]:

In this dialogue an attempt is made to define 'knowledge,' which ends, however, with a negative conclusion; several definitions were proposed and rejected, but no definition was put forward that would be considered satisfactory. The first of the proposed definitions, and the only one I shall consider, is formulated by Theaetetus thus: "*In my opinion, one who knows somehow perceives that which he knows, and, as it now appears to me, knowledge is nothing other than perception*". Socrates identifies this theory with the theory of Protagoras, that "*man is the measure of all things*", that is to say: "*... as each thing appears to me, so it is for me, and as it appears to you, so in turn it is for you*". Socrates adds: "*It follows that sensation is always sensation of being, and as knowledge it is infallible*".

What interests me in this passage is precisely what Plato places in the mouth of Socrates. If we reformulate Socrates (= Plato), we obtain: "*Every thought (termed sensation!) of any person concerning anything – corresponds to a certain Being, that is, to a certain Virtual Reality*".

Further, Plato strives to prove that perception = sensation is not reliable 'knowledge,' and Russell examines in detail this argumentation of Plato, but this is already *epistemology* – that is, it lies far beyond the limits of our topic. The point is that I do not examine the *relationship* between Material and Virtual Realities, which is precisely what has occupied philosophers most of all throughout two and a half millennia. For me, a simple statement suffices: some objects of Virtual Reality are reflections ('images') of Material Reality, while others are not (and may become such, or may not).

4. Ockham (c. 1285, Ockham Surrey county, England – 1347, Munich, Duchy of Bavaria, Holy Roman Empire)

In Wikipedia one can read about him that –

William Ockham (or of Ockham) (Engl. William of Ockham) – English philosopher, Franciscan³ monk from Ockham, a small village in Surrey county in Southern England.

A proponent of nominalism⁴, he believed that only the individual exists, and that universals exist only through abstract thinking in the human mind, and beyond this possess no metaphysical essence. He is considered one of

³ **Franciscans** – a Catholic mendicant monastic **order**, founded by Saint Francis of Assisi near Spoleto in 1208 with the aim of preaching apostolic poverty, asceticism, and love of neighbor to the people.

⁴ Nominalism (Lat. Nominalis – pertaining to names, nominal, from nomen – name) – a philosophical doctrine according to which the names of such concepts as "animal" <...> – are not proper names of integral entities, but common names (universals), a kind of variable in place of which concrete names can be substituted

the fathers of modern epistemology and modern philosophy as a whole, as well as one of the greatest logicians of all time.

Here is what Russell writes about Ockham himself and about his philosophy:

Ockham is best known for an aphorism that is absent from his works, but which nevertheless received the name 'Ockham's razor.' This aphorism states: "*Entities should not be multiplied without necessity*". Although Ockham never uttered such a phrase, he did express a thought that to a considerable extent inclines toward the same, namely: "*It is futile to do with more what can be done with less*". In other words, if in any science everything can be interpreted without assuming one or another hypothetical entity, then there is no need to assume it [Russell, 2001, p. 321]

<...>

Russell then expounds in detail Ockham's understanding of universals:

Terms relating to things themselves are called "terms of first intention"; terms relating to terms themselves are called "terms of second intention". Science employs terms of first intention; logic employs those of second intention. The peculiarity of *metaphysical* terms consists in the fact that they designate both things designated by words of first intention and things designated by words of second intention. There are only six metaphysical terms: being, thing, something, one, true, good<...>. The peculiarity of these terms consists in the fact that they can all be predicated of one another. But in logic one can manage without them.

Things are cognized, not forms generated by the mind; these forms are not that *which* is cognized, but that *by means of which* things are cognized. Universals (in logic) represent merely terms or concepts, asserting something about many other terms or concepts. *Universal, genus, species*– all these are terms of second intention and therefore cannot designate *things*. <...> A Universal is simply a sign of many things. <...> In explaining human cognition, Ockham never admits that Universals are *things*. The views of Socrates are similar to the views of Plato, he asserts, but not because there exists a third *thing* called similarity. Similarity represents a term of second intention and is a product of our mind. (All these thoughts are magnificent). [Russell, 2001, pp. 321–322].

I completely agree with Russell in his assessment of Ockham! In essence, Ockham set forth my metaphysics 650 years ago ... For everywhere he speaks of the products of our mind – he speaks of objects of Virtual Reality. Thus, what is new in my metaphysics is only the terminology, but not the essence, which was set forth by William Ockham.

5. Descartes (31 March 1596, La Haye, province of Touraine, now Descartes, department of Indre-et-Loire – 11 February 1650, Stockholm).

Wikipedia states about him thus:

(for example, instead of the common name "human" – the proper names "Peter," "Paul," "Anna," "Mary," etc.). <...> Universals, according to nominalism,– are names of names, and not entities (as for scholastic realism) or concepts (as for conceptualism): "...if we say that a living being, stone, spirit or anything else are universals, this should be understood <...> only thus, that the corresponding words <...>, common to many things: representations (conceptus), corresponding to these things in our mind, are only images and phantasms (imagines et phantasmata) of various living beings and other things"<...> .

René Descartes (<...> Lat. Renatus Cartesius – Cartesius); – French philosopher, mathematician, mechanician, physicist and physiologist, creator of analytical geometry and modern algebraic notation, author of the method of radical doubt in philosophy, mechanism in physics, precursor of reflexology.

Russell evaluates Descartes extremely highly:

«René Descartes (1596–1650) is usually considered, and I think rightly, the founder of modern philosophy. He is the first person of great philosophical abilities whose views were profoundly influenced by the new physics and astronomy. Although it is true that much from scholasticism is preserved in his theories, he nevertheless does not adhere to the foundations laid by his predecessors, but attempts to create anew a complete philosophical edifice. Nothing like this had occurred since Aristotle, and this was a sign of revived self-confidence stemming from the progress of science. His works exude a freshness that, after Plato, could not be found in any famous philosopher who preceded him [Russell, 2001, p. 372].

Russell expounds the views of Descartes and his Dutch pupil Geulincx on the relationship between soul and body: it appears as though the soul controls the movements of the body, although in reality both these substances are independent of one another:

«The theory that emerged had two merits. The first was that it made the soul in a certain sense completely independent of the body, since the soul was never under the influence of the body. The second was that it made possible the recognition of the fundamental principle: "*One substance cannot act upon another*". For there existed two substances – mind and matter, and they were so different that interaction between them seemed incomprehensible. Geulincx's theory explained the appearance of interaction, while denying, at the same time, its reality" [Russell, 2001, p. 375]. <...>

"Descartes's philosophy <...> firstly, <...> led to the completion or almost to the completion of the dualism of mind and matter, which was begun by Plato and developed largely for religious reasons by Christian philosophy. <...> The Cartesian system depicts two parallel but mutually independent worlds: the world of mind and the world of matter—each of which can be studied independently of the other. The notion that mind does not set the body in motion was a new idea, expressed explicitly by Geulincx and implicitly by Descartes." [Russell, 2001, pp. 378–379].

Thus, if we replace the Cartesian term 'soul' (which he believed resided in the pineal gland...) with the term 'consciousness,' and the term 'body' with the term 'matter,'—Descartes, and subsequently his student Geulincx, asserted the independence of Consciousness and Matter, that is, in the philosophical sense—their sovereign reality. True, we now know firmly that the Mind is secondary in relation to the Body, that is, ***non-material Consciousness is nevertheless a product of Matter***. Nevertheless, what is important for us here is that a clear understanding of reality (that is, Being, existence) as both material and virtual was undoubtedly present in Descartes and Geulincx in the 17th century.

Let us note, incidentally, that Descartes' famous formula *cogito ergo sum* – '*I think, therefore I exist*' – is erroneously interpreted as '*I think, therefore I exist*,' for the existence of the material body (of the thinking subject) is by no means determined by one of its functions. This formula should be interpreted precisely the other way around: '*I exist, therefore I can think*.' A causal relationship does

exist here, although not strictly necessary (for example, when I sleep, I exist, but I do not think). However, according to Russell, Descartes himself did not acknowledge this:

'Since thought is the essence of mind, the mind must always think, even during deep sleep' [Russell, 2001, p. 377].

6. Berkeley (12 March 1685 –14 January 1753).

Wikipedia says of him:

George Berkeley (Engl. George Berkeley; — Irish philosopher, known for his system of spiritualistic philosophy; Bishop of Cloyne (Engl. Cloyne) in Ireland. He consistently developed the thesis that 'being is either that which is perceived or the one who perceives'.

Although all metaphysics is a tedious matter, it is to George Berkeley that we all owe the spark of merriment in the Marxism-Leninism that was taught to us! For Soviet students (confirmed materialists) — Berkeley was portrayed as a true idealistic idiot: just imagine, this half-mad bishop concluded that matter does not exist at all!!

And although George Berkeley was by no means an idiot, he amused not only us, as Russell [Russell, 2001, p. 429] also testifies:

George Berkeley became famous for his denial of the existence of matter – a denial which he supported with a series of ingenious arguments. He maintained that material objects exist only by being perceived. To the objection that in such a case a tree, for example, would cease to exist if no one were looking at it, he replied that God always perceives everything; if God did not exist, then what we consider to be material objects would have a discontinuous life, suddenly arising at the moment when we look at them; but as it happens, thanks to God's perception both trees, and cliffs, and stones exist as constantly as common sense supposes. This, in his view, constitutes a weighty argument in favor of God's existence. Ronald Knox's limerick expounds Berkeley's theory of material objects thus:⁵

There was a young man who said:
"God must think it exceedingly funny
If He finds that this tree
Continues to exist
Even when there's no one in the yard".

Reply:

Dear Sir, Your astonishment is strange:
I am always in the yard, which is why the tree
Will continue to exist,
Observed by Your obedient servant God.

Recounting the philosophical works of Berkeley (who, incidentally, abandoned philosophy quite early, devoting himself entirely to tar-water,

⁵ **Ronald Knox** (17 February 1888, Leicestershire – 24 August 1957, London)— English religious figure and [writer](#), author of [detective novels](#). (Wikipedia).

which "*gladdens but does not inebriate*"), Russell humorously remarks on the concepts of "mind" and "matter":

It remains to ask whether any meaning can be attributed to the words 'mind' and 'matter.' Everyone knows that 'mind' is what the idealist thinks nothing exists except, and 'matter' is what the materialist thinks the same about. I hope the reader also knows that idealists are virtuous, whereas materialists are immoral [Russell, 2001, p. 436].

So then, what is valuable for us in Berkeley's metaphysics? The answer is evident: the assertion of the independent existence of Virtual Reality. At the same time, it is utterly immaterial that Berkeley recognized nothing else, nothing material. – This is his full right; as modern liberals would say, these are his sacred human rights.

7. Kant (April 22 1724, Königsberg, Prussia –February 121804, *ibid.*).
Wikipedia states about him:

Immanuel Kant (German Immanuel Kant <...>); – German philosopher, founder of German classical philosophy, standing at the boundary between the epochs of the Enlightenment and Romanticism.

<...> Kant rejected the dogmatic method of cognition and believed that instead one must adopt as a foundation the method of critical philosophizing, the essence of which consists in investigating reason itself, the boundaries that the human mind can reach through reason, and studying the particular modes of human cognition. Kant's principal philosophical work is the 'Critique of Pure Reason.' The initial problem for Kant is the question 'How is pure knowledge possible?'<...>. This concerns above all the possibility of pure mathematics and pure natural science ('pure' meaning 'non-empirical,' a priori, or extra-experiential). Kant formulated the indicated question in terms of the distinction between analytical and synthetic judgments – 'How are synthetic judgments a priori possible?' By 'synthetic' judgments Kant understood judgments with an increment of content in comparison with the content of the concepts entering into the judgment. Kant distinguished these judgments from analytical judgments, which reveal the meaning of concepts. Analytical and synthetic judgments differ in whether the content of the judgment's predicate follows from the content of its subject <...> (such are analytical judgments) or, conversely, is added to it 'from outside' (such are synthetic judgments). The term 'a priori' signifies 'independent of experience,' in contradistinction to the term 'a posteriori'—'derived from experience.'

As is well known, Immanuel Kant is considered the greatest philosopher of the Modern Era. In his famous 'Critique of Pure Reason,' he analyzes in detail the concept of space inherent in our thinking, for the description of which he proposed four metaphysical arguments. In particular, as presented by Russell, the second metaphysical argument is as follows:

Space is a necessary representation a priori, which underlies all external perceptions, since we cannot imagine that space should not exist, whereas we can imagine that nothing exists in space [Russell, 2001, p. 472].

To this Russell objects:

The second metaphysical argument asserts that one can imagine that nothing exists in space, but one cannot imagine that space itself does not exist. It seems to me that a serious argument cannot be based on what one can and cannot imagine [Russell, 2001, p. 472].

Since it is quite clear that Space pertains to the Virtual rather than to the material, then in order to reformulate Russell's objection, one need only replace the word 'imagine' with the word 'think'. Then we obtain: Kant admitted that Virtual Reality exists if it can be 'represented'—that is, thought about. And if it cannot—then it does not exist... That is, all of this 235 years ago—was clearly understood by Kant...

8. James(January 111842,New York–August 261910,Chocorua,Carroll County).

One can learn about him from Wikipedia:

William James (in older editions also Jemes,Engl.William James)—Americanphilosopherandpsychologist, one of the founders and leading representative ofpragmatismandfunctionalism. Often named by authors of textbooks and scholarly works as the father of modern psychology. Elder brother of the writer Henry James.

<...>

Russell writes extensively about James, whom he admires (although I did not understand everything):

James's doctrine of radical empiricism was first proclaimed in 1904 in an essay entitled 'Does Consciousness Exist?'. The primary purpose of this essay is the denial of the subject-object relation as a fundamental principle. Prior to this time, philosophers considered it self-evident that there existed a type of phenomenon called 'knowledge,' in which one entity, the knower or subject, knows another knowable thing or object. The knower is regarded as mind or soul; the knowable object may be a material object, an eternal essence, another mind or, in self-consciousness, identical with the knower. Nearly everything in conventional philosophy was closely bound up with the dualism of subject and object. If one does not accept the existence of the distinction between subject and object as fundamental, then the distinction between mind and matter, the contemplative ideal, and the traditional notion of 'truth' – all require radical reconceptualization.

As for me, I am convinced that on this question James is partially right, and for this reason alone deserves to occupy an honored place among philosophers. I held a different point of view until he and those who agree with him convinced me of the truth of his teaching.

<...> What he actually denies is, roughly speaking, the view of consciousness as a "thing". He asserts that there is "only one primary substance or material of which everything in the world is composed". This substance he calls "pure experience". <...>

It can be seen that this doctrine abolishes the distinction between mind and matter, regarded as a distinction between two different "kinds" of what James calls "Stuff" (substance) [Russell, 2001, p. 526].

As we can see, James denies that mind and matter are simply two different kinds of 'substance,' that is, of the same matter; **he does not consider consciousness to be matter**, but for some reason also calls it 'pure experience.'

Thus, the penultimate among my predecessors who recognized the sovereignty (autonomous status) of Virtual Reality is the physician Henry James, founder of American philosophy.

9. Bergson (18 October 1859, Paris – 4 January 1941, *ibid.*)

Wikipedia states the following about him:

Henri Bergson (Fr. Henri Bergson); French philosopher, representative of intuitivism and philosophy of life]. <...> Laureate of the Nobel Prize in Literature of 1927 «*in recognition of his rich and vitalizing ideas, and the brilliant skill with which they have been presented*». Key works: *Creative Evolution* (L'Évolution créatrice. Paris, 1907) and *The Two Sources of Morality and Religion* (Les Deux sources de la morale et de la religion. Paris, 1932). <...>. In the late 1920s, due to illness, he gradually concentrated entirely on scholarly work. After the capitulation of France in 1940, Bergson returned all his orders and awards and, rejecting the authorities' offer to exempt him from anti-Jewish edicts, being sick and weak, stood in a hours-long queue to register himself as a Jew. He died in German-occupied Paris from pneumonia. <...>

Bergson affirms as genuine and primordial reality life, which, existing in a certain wholeness, differs from matter and spirit. Matter and spirit, taken by themselves, are products of its disintegration. The fundamental concepts by means of which the philosopher defines the essence of 'life' are 'duration', 'creative evolution', and 'vital impulse'. Life cannot be grasped by intellect. The intellect is capable of creating 'abstract' and 'general' concepts; it is the activity of reason, whereas to reproduce reality in all its organicity and universality is possible only by recreating it. This is within the power only of intuition, which, being an immediate experience of the object, 'penetrates into its intimate essence.'

Russell expounds this much more briefly:

Henri Bergson was the leading French philosopher of our century <...>. Bergson's philosophy, unlike most systems of the past, is dualistic. The World for him is divided into two fundamentally different parts: on one side – life, on the other matter, or, more precisely, that inert "something" which the intellect regards as matter. [Russell, 2001, p. 519].

That is, I learn from Wikipedia and from Russell (with the astonishment characteristic of the ignorant) that ***my immediate predecessor*** was none other than Henri Bergson! For it is evident that Bergson's division of the world into *matter* and *life* – this is precisely, one-to-one, the division of the world into the Material and the Virtual. For *life* may well be understood as entirely virtual, since all of its predicates (duration, creative evolution, and creative impulse) are purely virtual (non-material).

10. Spirit and Reality by Nikolai Berdyaev

Unfortunately, Russell completely overlooked the book 'Spirit and Reality' by the Russian religious philosopher Berdyaev (1874–1948, Obukhov, Kiev Governorate, Russian Empire), published in Paris in 1937.⁶

I downloaded this book and immediately discovered that Berdyaev calls the product of thought *Spirit*, that is, what we have called *virtual*, and he calls *Reality* what we call *material*. (I note that another Russian philosopher, Berdyaev's friend Lev Shestov, frequently uses the word 'natural' as a synonym for 'material'.)

And from the very first lines of his book, Berdyaev declares the sovereignty of the spiritual and the material, rejecting two extremes: both the purely materialist interpretation of Spirit by vulgar materialists and 'vitalists,' and the reverse—the denial of matter by extreme idealist-spiritualists who refused to acknowledge matter as 'objective reality,' but considered only Spirit 'real,' as a kind of '*substance of special quality*':

⁶ It is quite possible that Russell actually knew of Berdyaev – but did not consider him in his lectures 'on legitimate grounds' – since formally Berdyaev's writings do not belong to *Western philosophy*

«The World inclines toward the denial of the reality of spirit. It does not doubt only the reality of visible things that compel their own acknowledgment. But spirit is not a visible thing; it is not at all a thing among things. True, a diminished reality of spirit is acknowledged by all, even the most extreme materialists. This cannot be otherwise, because even those who deny the existence of spirit nevertheless possess it. But in this case spirit is acknowledged as an epiphenomenon of matter, a product of material processes. No one has ever been able to explain what this actually means. The materialist negation of spirit is ultimately an incorrect description of the realities given in experience, just as a description of light phenomena by a color-blind person is incorrect. The materialist resolves the difficulty by attributing to matter all the properties of spirit—reason, freedom, activity. More refined philosophical schools see in spirit not an epiphenomenon of matter, but an epiphenomenon of life, to which they ascribe inexhaustible creative force. This is a vitalistic understanding of spirit. Spiritualistic philosophical currents made the defense of the reality of spirit their specialty. Spiritualism typically understands spirit as substance, as a reality of special quality among the things of the natural world, but nonetheless a reality in the same sense. Philosophical thought has often naturalized spirit and introduced it, as the highest stage, into the hierarchy of the objective world. Spirit was understood as one of the objects, albeit an object of the highest order. This attributed to spirit a reality similar to the reality of objects of the objective world. But is it possible to attain the reality of spirit, to demonstrate its reality as an object in the world? Herein lies the entire acuteness of the problem standing before us. Philosophical thought, inclined toward objectification and toward the hypostatization of thought, identifies reality with objectivity. To demonstrate the reality of spirit means to demonstrate its objectivity.

All the remaining content of Berdyaev's book (extremely interesting for professional philosophers, especially for historians of philosophy) – is already superfluous for our topic, all the more so because, as a religious philosopher, he is most interested in religion within *Spirit*, particularly Christianity – '*God-human spirituality*'.

For our theme it is quite sufficient to conclude that Nikolai Berdyaev in 1937 formulated practically 1:1 the propositions I independently discovered 70 years later concerning (1) the non-material nature of the Virtual, that is, the product of human thought, (2) the sovereignty of Spirit, that is, the independent, real existence (= *Being*) of the Virtual.

Conclusion

Above were initially presented the propositions of my metaphysics—expounded axiomatically, without logical proofs. Being profoundly ignorant in philosophy, I arrived at them entirely independently. If I were a believer, I would say that they were given to me through *Revelation*. But since I am an inveterate obstinate atheist, there can be no question of any *revelations*. It is better to say that the thoughts I have set forth are the product of a certain 'intuition'; this is how one usually designates thoughts that come to mind suddenly—without any proofs.

After this, with the help of *Wikipedia* and Bertrand Russell's book '*A History of Western Philosophy*,' I undertook a 'survey' of genuine philosophers (adding Nikolai Berdyaev to them!) and discovered that my intuitive thoughts had in fact already been expressed in one form or another by great philosophers over the 2,500 years of philosophy's existence. Such a coincidence permits one to hope that my intuitive thoughts are not erroneous either.

1. The human being exists in a world that comprises two parts: the material and the non-material, termed the Virtual.

2. The existence of these parts has always been recognized by the majority of philosophers; what was essentially divergent in philosophy was not the

existence of these parts, but rather their interrelationships. According to whether the dominance of 'body, substance,' etc., or of 'spirit,' 'soul,' 'representation,' etc., was acknowledged, monist philosophers divided into materialists and idealists.

3. Both these parts are 'sovereign,' that is, entirely independent of one another. Such a relationship between the parts of the world has been recognized by only very few dualist philosophers. This— **is the first principal thesis of my metaphysics – the sovereign reality** (Being, existence) of objects of both the Material and the Virtual World.

4. Objects of the Material World consist of atoms (numbering around 100), and some may consist of elementary particles (protons, electrons, positrons, neutrinos, etc.).

5. The objects of the Virtual World are human thoughts (ideas, representations, concepts). They are generated by a material body—the brain—but are themselves not material; that is, they do not consist of atoms, elementary particles, or fields.

6. Despite the sovereign status of the Material and Virtual Worlds, they have different geological ages: on our planet, the Virtual appeared approximately 4.5 billion years later than the Material. This is the age of the appearance on planet Earth of the biological species *Homo sapiens*, which, unlike other creatures, possessed consciousness. **Thus, the Virtual is not simply a product of the brain** (the brain probably exists in all living creatures) – **but a product of Consciousness.**

7. Everything that can be thought about (that is, everything that can be generated by Consciousness) – exists, that is, has Being. Correspondingly, the reverse thesis is also true: what cannot be thought about – does not exist in the Virtual World. Thus, in particular, believed Socrates. This is – **the second main thesis of my metaphysics – the reality of any objects of the Virtual World.**

8. This paradoxical thesis generates the most astonishing consequences! For example, it implies the reality of God, upon which all world religions are founded—religions that powerful modern science has been unable to eradicate. The subtlety here consists in the fact that God is not material; He is an object of the Virtual World. And if thought has been given to Him (and humanity has occupied itself with nothing else for three thousand years), then He exists virtually.

9. It is evident that our metaphysics lies mainly apart from epistemology—the theory of knowledge. As is well known, epistemology investigates the correspondence between thoughts (the non-material) and natural objects (the material). The central problem within it is to what extent our knowledge and representations ('images') concerning objects of the Material World are 'correct,' and, correspondingly, to what extent they may be 'false.' But in view of the sovereign reality of the Material and Virtual Realities, this problem does not concern us, since any objects of the Virtual World are 'correct' by their very definition.

The epistemological aspect in our metaphysics can emerge only when an object of the Virtual World can simultaneously correlate in some manner with an

object of the Material World. For instance, the virtual object God possesses no material correlate whatsoever, whereas the virtual object 'Black Hole' undoubtedly does; therefore, physicists are highly interested in ascertaining—precisely which one. Nevertheless (and herein lies the paradox of our metaphysics!), whatever the Black Hole may prove to be in material terms, any thought we entertain about it is correct...

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